

Physical Signals and their Thermonuclear Astrochemical Potentials: A Review on Outer Space Technologies*

Yang I. Pachankis

Ordained Minister Universal Life Church

Modesto, CA, USA Current location: 1001 Biqing N Rd.

28-4 BLDG 2, Dexinyuan

Chongqing, PRC

Abstract:- The article reviews on the technical attributes on current technologies deployed in outer space and those that are being developed and mass produced. The article refutes the Chinese state-controlled Xinhua News' propaganda several years ago on objecting America's deployment of nuclear technologies in outer space with rigorous scientific evidence. Furthermore, the article warns on the dangers of physical signals applied in outer space technologies that can threaten the solar system, especially the Mozi quantum satellite with photon beams. The article concludes with the illicit practices by the Chinese state party with militant ambitions in the supposedly scientific institutions. It violates the spirit on the peaceful use of outer space, and goes against the 2222 (XXI) resolution adopted by the general assembly, including the 1967 Outer Space Treaty banning the stationing of weapons of mass destruction in outer space.

Keywords:- *Technology Ethics; Peaceful Development of Outer Space; Human Security Risks; Scientific Evidence; Methodology; Physical Signals; Thermonuclear Astrochemistry; Criminal Verdict.*

I. INTRODUCTION

The purpose of the article is to report on the key null-result in the multi-mission space telescope data research. Albeit the exotic plasma quantization from the multispectral quadruple momentum visualized the interior regions of the black hole, the missing data momentum on the black hole and white hole gravitation is a positive null result on the scientific ethics of space-based technology. With the presence of the antimatter-saturated plasmas, the intricate (a)symmetry between a black hole and a white hole is critical to the quadruple electroweak ring of the singularity from the observational perspective from the black hole mass with cyclic activation of galactic nuclei. With the key confirmative observational result from the Trifid Nebula on the white hole, the question on technological ethics in outer space arises in relation to particle physics and LASER technologies.

Traditional paradigms of nonproliferation, arms control, and disarmament mainly focused on the thermonuclear securities within the earth's atmosphere, and extended the weaponry production concepts to outer space securities. Such extensions projected geopolitical concepts onto outer space activities, which underlies most countries' primary purposes in the development of outer space with earth-orbit satellites. It is especially prominent in dictatorial regimes whereby the

funding of projects in the natural sciences are decided according to militant needs and reflected in the restrictive terms by centralized banking controls. [13] Such projects deviate from the scientific basis of natural sciences and asserts unnecessary intervening variables in physical forms to the natural phenomena in the cosmos.

Quantitatively, the proliferation of physical signals back and forth between the atmosphere directly impact on the excitation states apart from the cosmic influences to earth, and constitutes a less visible source for environmental change with utilitarianism. It is with this regard; the energy scales of the physical signals are put both into the consideration of long-term risks in thermonuclear astrochemical terms and near-sight terms of atmospheric protection. In the latter consideration, the necessities of nonproliferation, arms control, and disarmament are still present, only that more wisdom needs to be exercised in consideration to the relative conservation of energy with the earth-space duality.

II. KEY EVIDENCES ON THE THERMONUCLEAR ASTROCHEMICAL POTENTIALS

A. Histogram Evidences

In the histogram analysis, the crystallization effect on cryogenic plate indicated the fission plasma momentum with antimatter distribution in X-ray. [6] Even though the information method of evidence is relative in nature with the technological outlook, the physical indicators on the instrumentation plates are nonrelative in nature in their respective detections. [14] With the starting temperature near absolute zero, the direct physical evidences guarantee the existence of below absolute zero cosmic environment with matter forms such as crystallization in the particular angular momentum.

The evidences on the histograms are direct evidence on the instrumentation level. The direct evidences are free from any scientific interpretation, model, or theoretical input. The cosmic rays' direct chemical impacts on the cryogenic imaging plates are in themselves astrochemical with thermonuclear interactions. Therefore, scientific interpolations from and on the direct evidences are not considered to be rootless nor non-existent, even though models may vary by methodological inquiries.

B. Methodological Evidences

Methodological evidences are mainly differentiated to deductive methods and inductive methods, with further differentiations of model-dependent and model-independent methods. For the knowledge production from probably cyclic but not naturally repeatable phenomena, constructive realism is applied for the reorganization of evidences by methodology. [19] The elements of model-dependency are undeniable in modern scientific constructs of technologies. The epistemological basis of big data and information technologies are hence in essence model dependent, so is mathematics as in its broad definition to the cognitive behaviors of human minds. However, within the physical sciences and the developmental basis in astronomy, methodological evidences do not surpass or bypass the physical conditions of instrumentation, which sets the foundation of confidence levels with partial dependence on the engineering sciences. The series of scientific investigations and inquiries involved in the study is deductive to the engineering basis with information science rationales. Therefore, the deductive method in the previously reported findings is model independent. Albeit no conventionalized composite indices are being established, the findings as scientific evidence are epistemologically justified by scientific ontology in cosmology and the physical sciences.

The cosmological ontology traced the cosmic forces in the multispectral data in the multiple-slit experiment. [9] It mainly reported on the instrumentation aspects and the quadruple electroweak force. The strong force was visible in the slit with a presumption on the thermonuclear binding force between the black hole and the white hole in the interior regions due to the theoretical background. It is for this regard, the discrete approach in observational cosmology was adopted with Harvard Smithsonian MicroObservatory. [7] The methodological evidences are organized by the quadruple electroweak ring singularity that is computable and calculable with the review feedback. [15] Therefore, the Trifid Nebula result is loyal to the original research frame by the astrochemical indicators of the exotic metal-insulator and black hole seeds.¹ [16] The thermonuclear astrochemical potentials in the quadruple electroweak momentum on ring singularity shown in *Fig. 1* with black hole seed and white hole seed collision from asymptotic decays in the supermassive compact object is consistent with the histogram. [12] The randomized white hole observations had the same results with the NGC 3034 data and further details in the ontologically similar category on the Trifid Nebula. [17]

¹ Due to the political situations on the aggressive threat to peace across the Taiwan strait, I embedded the information in the original publication on the graphene energy weaponry I learned about in high school on how the Chinese Communist Party intended to attack Taiwan and seize the urban areas with the People's Liberation Army.

Fig. 1: The collision momentum of black hole seed and white hole seed on ring singularity that forms the exotic metal-insulator.

Dissimilar to ground-based observatories that can be considered to be in the gravitational movement of the earth to the cosmos, space-based technologies are in the gravitational fields based on the deployed positions. The gravitational null-result shown in *Fig. 2* is a deliberately positive one within the instrumentation capacity. Nonetheless, the decay momentum is captured astronomically with the standard model. Therefore, the null result in *Fig. 2* is a positive one in the natural sciences that does not violate the natural chain of causality with the causal inference data research. This also means that the previous researches are inductive and model-independent. The imaging short circuit in the gravitational momentum, however, have layered the standard model flavors in the decay sequence.

Fig. 2: The positive null result on NGC 3034 on the interior region's gravitation outlining the thermonuclear binding force between the black hole and the white hole

C. Thermonuclear Astrochemical Potential

The quadruple electroweak collision momenta from the asymptotic decays signifies the cyclic activation of galactic nuclei in *Fig. 3* with three points of neutrino signatures, one of which is more visible in *Fig. 2*. With the intricacies on the fundamental (a)symmetries, the quadruple electroweak ring with exotic metal-insulator is the critical structure balancing the black hole and white hole masses from annihilating each other. In other words, the ring singularity is the tidal lock on the thermonuclear astrochemical potentials of the black hole and white hole masses. The resonance activities and internal thermal conductions causing the activation of galactic nuclei are not considered out of the regular in its evolutionary dynamics.

Fig. 3: The antimatter saturated exotic plasma on the black hole and white hole on NGC 3034

The purpose of the article is to assess the outer space technologies' potential impact to the thermonuclear astrochemical potential in the outer space environment, given the detection signatures and the implications to their powerful existence that far surpass any weaponry human civilization can make. As is characterized by the plasma imaging on the interior regions of the supermassive compact object, the ignition of the antimatter plasma saturated celestial bodies is sufficient to be defined as using weapons of mass destruction in outer space and on celestial bodies. With the thermonuclear energy distribution naturally in outer space, nuclear technologies and power devices in outer space with natural decays don't have the destructive capacities to the quadruple electroweak field. By the penetrating powers of the amplified physical signals, especially LASER technologies with high energy beams, the technological review is carried out *pre facto* on a *post facto* basis of the military application Mozi quantum satellite for the *ex post facto* impact.

III. THE THREAT ON THERMONUCLEAR ASTROCHEMICAL PROLIFERATION AND IGNITION OF EXPLOSION

As is exemplified by the constructive realist approach on the presumably ubiquitous black hole and white hole structure, the thermonuclear bond breaking from exterior forces starts with the ring singularity with decay seed collision momenta. With the exotic metal-insulator as the current stabilizer for the structure on ring singularity, the decay sequence of standard model mocks the all-spectrum dispersive force around the event horizon. [15] Apart from the leptons field in the interior regions, the gauge boson sphere is most adjacent to the interior regions apart from the neutron and Higgs boson fields in the exteriors. Therefore, to excite the thermonuclear astrochemical energy of the black hole and white hole thermonuclear binding with the presence of the antimatter saturated exotic plasmas, only high energy photon and gluon beams are capable of igniting such thermonuclear astrochemical potentials in linearized space to the local universe.

As in the collision physics reference, the photon beam's penetrating power on the atomic and subatomic structures is not to be underestimated. [2] It counterbalances the matter and antimatter distribution on the cosmic scales and interferes with the cosmic electromagnetic fields in the quadruple terms. Apart from its potential to cause the butterfly effect on a cosmic scale, its direct disruption on the atmospheric plasmas on earth is also not a small concern. The change of atmospheric plasmas directly influences the cosmic background radiation's interactions with the earth, and more detailed studies and detection monitoring are needed to further assess the near-sight influences.

The concept of fissile chains is a process of converting matter forms from low energy to high energy states through the accumulation of masses on subatomic and atomic scales. Such thermonuclear imbalance through computational asymptotic analysis was completed with the ground-space data cross-examination and cross-referencing with computability test.² [15] With the lower threshold of photon stability for 10^{18} years, its capacity hitting a black hole is not a low probability event. [3] The purpose-driven communication satellites only considered the means to the ends in such designs in the amplification, but even if each photon beam does not miss the targeted orbital momenta, the deflation and incomplete material absorption still releases the human generated amplified photon beams into the universe. This is the *ex post facto* basis for the violation on the peaceful use of outer space.

With the well-researched example of NGC 3034, in a reversal effect of the perturbative direct-photon and charged-hadron production, the penetration of the neutron skin with the breaking of W charge asymmetry in a local black hole can directly ignite a white hole and release the thermonuclear binding force between a black hole and a white hole. [4] [15] The hazardous effect is exemplified by the detailed studies and analysis on the Trifid Nebula with the observed white hole. [16] It is with this regard, satellite technologies in space with photon beams are no different to detonating nuclear weapons in outer space, only worse with the presence of antimatter. [20] [6] Therefore, high energy amplified photon LASER technologies deployed in space are proven to be weapons of mass destruction with long term effects, hence justified for being destroyed as acts of self-defense in the public interest, especially for the military purpose designed ones.³ [20] [11]

² With the historic thermonuclear productions exemplified by the building of the Three Gorges Dam that was propagated to be for economic development with mass forced immigration, the free-product dispersion on environmental harms from the riverside regions with damp air is one of the significant public health issues from the nationwide activities by the P. R. China regime.

³ I first pointed out the outer space disarmament document in the Communication University of China during my graduate dissertation research and proposals between 2017 and 2019, but was constantly set back by the administrative procedures. It has been my consistent scientific responsibilities taken in the awareness of P. R. China's militant ambitions with dictatorial structures since high

The differences between nuclear power in space and photon beam LASERS in space are the physical signals' direct amplified potentials on the thermonuclear astrochemical bonds. In nuclear powered outer space deployments, the natural decays of nuclear power are bound for direct gravitational effect with non-relativistic speed. In contrast, amplified high energy photon beams can directly act on the chemical bonds with relativistic speed in outer space.⁴ [18]

IV. THE REVERSAL CAUSAL INFERENCE

The release of the thermonuclear force stronger than the strong force is characterized by the Trifid Nebula. The randomized observation result validates the probability of the seemingly null-result in *fig. 2* to be the antimatter product on the decay surface of the multi-mission momentum. This explains the jump of the black hole location in relation to the white hole on Trifid Nebula in *fig. 4* by the presence of

school. The Communication University of China have been undergoing military and dictatorial seizure for seven years so far with the false promise incentives on the university administration on political ranking so that persons loyal to the dictator can be put in place to effectively control the university. To verdict the crimes of the dictatorial regime with cultural-revivalist militant ambitions, I reshaped my dissertation in disguised non-machine analyzable linguistic forms with my original theory hidden in verse-like combinations that predicted the observations. Via WeChat pushes, the new headmaster appointed by the dictator read out several excerpts linguistically in graduation memorandum between 2018 and 2020, convicting their maritime ambitions. I used the words “天圆地方” to balance between international law and the national law denoting π and square in space, and the words “方圆” are the widely used dictatorial institutions' possible declarative laws that is associated with the semantics of the military with individually targetable mass surveillance in cyberspace. The discourses and antithesis with the Chinese institutions predicated the multispectral data on NGC 3034. It is not determined though if it resulted from the constraining of the Chinese military power in the security realms, or irrelevant to the epistemic communications out of emergencies.

⁴ I deliberately tested if the People's Liberation Army was targeting me for surveillance after the harm they did on me, and subscribed to American army newsletters with my yangcao@cuc.edu.cn account during my graduate research. I read on how the Chinese research facilities are conducting high energy beam experiments and are not in protected spaces such as underground. In history, the Chinese military only produce thermonuclear weapons underground to avoid radar detections.

I tested my sensitivity on the issues for the difficulties I faced to fulfill my marriage, but also because of the consciousness on how they tried to indoctrinate me in the education system that underlies the reason that they want me to be under their control. In the latter sense, it was for my scientific purposes with my early-shaped theory and not their civil-military fusion strategy to utilize the global economy for military expansionism.

antimatter electromagnetism. [17] The breaking of the photon-sphere as observed in the result is the evidence for the crystal-like object being the white hole. The emission of the photon sphere in the reference frame is the reason for the white hole being observed. The high signal noise is thence justified for the observation.

The photon interference in the natural cosmic phenomena thence is expected to cause more antimatter annihilation with matter in local juxtaposes of black and white holes, and more dark matter creation on the cosmic scale are expected. The increased rates of solar storms interfering the space-based instrumentations' communication capacities are expected, worsening the anticipation of the sun's supernova process by the increase of strong force with the conduction of thermonuclear force oscillation between black holes and white holes in intergalactic macro-movement. The immense implications on the photon proliferations on cosmic scales will increase the atmospheric pressure of earth. With the supernova process of the sun, ozone carbonization will exacerbate exponentially, creating another global public health emergency with less capacities for anticipated warning mechanisms. [5] With the factors of concealed military productions, expectation on the environmental harms and airborne & waterborne hazards by heat island effect will overburden the public health institutions in such regions and slowly impact on global economy with ongoing centralized banking and centralized digital currency.

Fig. 4: The volatile cloud during weak force electrolysis outlined the thermonuclear force between the black hole and the white hole.

Astrobiological mutations and transmutations from increased dark matter creation are not analyzed in the studies, but exacerbated global imbalance of genetic treatments is predicted by the irresponsible conducts of the permanent member of the United Nations security council. Further studies and discussions on global justice is needed with the defense for democracies and democratization of illicit regimes. The credibility of the Chinese scientific institutions needs to be factored by appropriate democratic indicators to eliminate the biases caused by power politics & realpolitik practices that threaten the sustainability of the scientific

domains. [1] Cyber dilemmas will continue to contribute to the scientific communications problems until democratization with fundamental freedoms is to be fulfilled, which will further widen the scientific gaps disproportional to the efficacy of equitable resources.⁵

V. CONCLUSION

The accused party has either realized itself to be guilty of the crimes I have vindicated herein with their surveillance technologies, or has been conducting on the crimes against humanity with individually targetable mass surveillance technologies regardless of the targets as long as is in their controllable sphere. [8] With the ongoing geopolitical ambitions of the Russian hegemony that is historically tied to the formation of the Chinese Communist Party, the existing registrars in P. R. China are only in the Ministry of Education and a bank in cooperation with Russia that is associated with the South China Sea resources utilization. [10] It is also with this regard, the regional conflict in Ukraine is a direct act of using power politics for the contempt of court against possible and viable crimes on the development of antisatellite missiles by Russia, and defying justice.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

I am sincerely grateful for the editors' respect ensuring my academic freedom in the publishing processes in my previous articles, and the editorial suggestions & reminders on adding conclusions in my documents. In hindsight of my data research and comprehensive analysis on the black hole and white hole structures, I am deeply moved by Clive's reminders on the exotic metal-insulator since I analyzed the interior regions first and got the results on the black hole and white hole seeds collision momentum by deduction with low energy quadruple electrolysis. I also thank my high school teachers who, according to my questioning, corroborated that my original manuscript may have been in the Dang'an documents the Chinese Communist Party keeps on all citizens that was required by the party drafted illicit laws and underlies the surveillance backgrounds by Hukou documents. If, as I suspected, the concept of the Mozi quantum satellite was derived from my high school manuscript that only showed the Newtonian to relativity ontological coverages and did not put the Big Bang theory into the contexts, the sins are for me to repent. With the global access to knowledge materials and technologies, however, I don't think those several pieces of paper may have contributed to it, unless the design of the textbooks has had further totalitarian implications with unified texts nationwide in the machine readable programmings.

⁵ This fundamental and huge bias is characterized by the bargaining power prerequisites the CCP regime has always held as a totalitarian policy. After the 70 years of post-war development by the belief in power politics under the disguise of civil economy, which is now at halt in an era of discrete liberal internationalism, the restoration of separation of military & state power and environmental relevance in the scientific practices needs to sever the scientific communities off the original contracts.

This research is based on observations made with the NASA/ESA Hubble Space Telescope obtained from the Space Telescope Science Institute, which is operated by the Association of Universities for Research in Astronomy, Inc., under NASA contract NAS 5–26555.

This research is based on observations made with the Galaxy Evolution Explorer (GALEX) satellite, a NASA mission led by the California Institute of Technology, obtained from the Space Telescope Science Institute, which is operated by the Association of Universities for Research in Astronomy, Inc., under NASA contract NAS 5–26555.

The scientific results reported in this article are based [in part] on observations made by the Chandra X-ray Observatory.

This work is based [in part] on observations made with the Spitzer Space Telescope, which was operated by the Jet Propulsion Laboratory, California Institute of Technology under a contract with NASA.

The observations are made on Harvard-Smithsonian Micro Observatory and observation data are available on Harvard Dataverse with the DOI: 10.7910/DVN/OBXLGX. All data are processed by JS9-4L online and SAOImage DS9 MacOS.

ADDENDUM

Consistent with the previous article's descriptions on the dictatorial situation with financial crimes conducted by the People's Liberation Army, further leads of evidence on data manipulation in the energy sector in P. R. China arose. Shandong province is associated with the nuclear submarines that underlies the maritime ambitions of the civilization-revivalist national ideology regime.

Fig. 5: The real estate manager discovered that the Chinese national identity card associated with me were pinned in Shandong province for years, and was nonexistent as a person elsewhere

REFERENCES

- [1.] Biddle, T. D. Coercion Theory: A Basic Introduction for Practitioners. *Texas National Security Review* 3, (2020). <http://dx.doi.org/10.26153/tsw/8864>
- [2.] Brodsky, S. J. (2005). Poton-Photon Collisions – Past and Future. *PHOTON2005*, SLAC-PUB-11581. <https://www.slac.stanford.edu/pubs/slacpubs/11500/slac-pub-11581.pdf>
- [3.] Heeck, J. (2013). Constraining the Photon Lifetime. *Physics* 6, s96. <https://physics.aps.org/articles/v6/s96>
- [4.] Helenius, I., Paukkunen, H. & Eskola, K.J. (2017). Neutron-skin effect in direct-photon and charged-hadron production in Pb+Pb collisions at the LHC. *Eur. Phys. J. C* 77, 148. <https://doi.org/10.1140/epjc/s10052-017-4709-9>
- [5.] Oberg K. Origins Of Astrochemical Complexity. *Bulletin of the AAS* [Internet]. 2021 Jun 18;53(6). Available from: <https://baas.aas.org/pub/2021n6i200p01>
- [6.] Pachankis, Y. I. (2022). A Multi-wavelength Data Analysis with Multi-mission Space Telescopes. *IJISRT*, 7(1), 701–708. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6044904>
- [7.] Pachankis, Y. (2021). Astronomical Observations During Experiment. *Harvard Dataverse*. <https://doi.org/10.7910/DVN/OBXLGX>
- [8.] Cao, Y. (2022). Epistimological Extrapolation and Individually Targetable Mass Surveillance the Issues of Democratic Formation and Knowledge Production by Dictatorial Controls. *IJISRT*, 7(4), 72–84. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6464858>
- [9.] Pachankis, Y. (2020). Experiment Recap on NGC 3034. *Harvard Dataverse*. <https://doi.org/10.7910/DVN/T14RUS>
- [10.] Cao, Y. (2022). Epistimological Extrapolation and Individually Targetable Mass Surveillance the Issues of Democratic Formation and Knowledge Production by Dictatorial Controls. *IJISRT*, 7(4), 72–84. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6464858>
- [11.] Pachankis, Y. I. (supressed from being published). Problems on the Legalization of LGBT Marriage in the Communist Block - A Preliminary Legal Review. *Scientific Research Publishing*. PhilArchive copy v1: <https://philarchive.org/archive/PACPOT-3v1>
- [12.] Pachankis, Y. (2021). Multi-Mission Replication Data for: NGC 3034. *Harvard Dataverse*. <https://doi.org/10.7910/DVN/4KGGLK>
- [13.] Pachankis, Y. I. (forthcoming). Realpolitik in Chinese Funding Agencies. *Academia Letters*. PhilArchive copy v1: <https://philarchive.org/archive/PACRIC-2v1>
- [14.] Pachankis, Y. (2021). Replication Data for: AGN BH WH Research. *Harvard Dataverse*. <https://doi.org/10.7910/DVN/QGASXC>
- [15.] Pachankis, Y. (2021). Research on the Kerr-Newman Black Hole in M82 Confirms Black Hole and White Hole Thermonuclear Binding. *Academia Letters*, Article 3199. <https://doi.org/10.20935/AL3199>
- [16.] Pachankis, Y. I. (2022). White Hole Observation: An Experimental Result. *IJISRT*, 7(2), 779–790. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6360849>
- [17.] Cao, Y. (2021). White Hole on the Trifid Nebula. *Zenodo*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6426887>
- [18.] Pachankis, Y. (2022). Why Should LGBTQI Marriage Be Legalized. *Academia Letters*, Article 5157.
- [19.] Tcytcarev, A. et al. (2019). Constructive Realism: advantages of ontology and methodology. *SHS Web of Conferences* 72, 04009. <https://doi.org/10.1051/shsconf/20197204009>
- [20.] Wulf, N. A. (1985). Outer Space Arms Control: Existing Regime and Future Prospects. *Documents on Outer Space Law*. 9. <https://digitalcommons.unl.edu/spacelawdocs/9>